

Journal of the Orthodox Center for the Advancement of Biblical Studies

Vol. 13, No. 1 (2024)

The Pursuit of Happiness down from Jerusalem

The Parable of the Good Samaritan in the Light of the Kingdom

Daniel Ayuch

Introduction

Since 2012, the UN has designated March 20th as the International Day of Happiness “to promote happiness, well-being, and a more compassionate world.” Consequently, for several years, the media have inundated us with statistics from the *World Happiness Report* around this date.¹ The increasing interest of global politics in promoting happiness brings the topic to the forefront for Christian theological analysis. This study contributes to this extensive task by examining the subject from a biblical perspective, particularly through the texts of the Gospel of St. Luke. In a predominantly capitalist world, consumerism, individualism, and meritocracy are widely promoted. Hedonistic happiness prevails in public opinion, although occasional warnings about its limitations and restrictions can be found.²

The Gospel according to Luke addresses happiness in various ways, using rich terminology derived not only from the Hebrew Bible and the Septuagint but also from Hellenistic culture and thought. One of the most notable texts on this subject is the Beatitudes in the Sermon on the Plain. In biblical tradition, the happy are referred to as μακάριοι, a term that contrasts sharply with the Greek concept of *eudaimonia*, which is central to non-Christian Greek philosophy and literature but entirely absent from the Bible.³ This study examines the interaction between the Beatitudes and the

¹ See John F. Helliwell, Richard Layard, Jeffrey D. Sachs, Jan-Emmanuel De Neve, Lara B. Akinin, & Shun Wang (Eds.). *World Happiness Report 2024*. University of Oxford: Wellbeing Research Centre, 2024.

<https://worldhappiness.report/ed/2024/>. This report, compiled by institutions such as the University of Oxford, the Gallup Institute, and the UN, serves as a valuable resource that underscores the increasing global focus on prioritizing happiness. A key feature is the ranking of countries, with Finland maintaining the top position for several years. In the most recent report, US is ranked 23rd, while Lebanon is 142nd out of 143 participating countries. The report is particularly useful for governments and social service organizations, as it highlights that happiness includes well-being, personal fulfillment, education, employment, and health. The 2024 edition places greater emphasis on individuals and age groups.

² Xosé Gabriel Vázquez. Opinión. Informe Mundial de la Felicidad. En: Economía Digital Galicia. <https://www.economiadigital.es/galicia/opinion/informe-mundial-de-la-felicidad.html>.

³ For a detailed study of the term see the recent article by Carlos J. Gil Arbiol. El Buen Samaritano y la proximidad del herido: La aportación del naciente cristianismo a la búsqueda de la felicidad. *Carthaginensia* 40, 77, 2024, 2-10. In this article Gil Arbiol also analyzes the Beatitudes and the parable of the Good Samaritan from a predominantly social and

parable of the Good Samaritan, as both discuss the fulfillment of the person in this world and the Kingdom of God. The Beatitudes proclaim a new wisdom, while the parable demonstrates how to apply it by challenging the principles imposed by authoritarianism and power. The Gospel of Luke proposes a reversal of the human condition as a theological and wisdom-based principle.

Luke's Gospel is unique in its approach to happiness, intertwining it with themes of compassion, mercy, and social justice. The beatitudes, for instance, offer a radical redefinition of happiness, one that is not based on material wealth or social status but on faith. This redefinition is further illustrated in the parable of the Good Samaritan, which emphasizes the importance of loving one's neighbor and acting with kindness and generosity, even towards those who are traditionally seen as outsiders or enemies. By juxtaposing these two texts, we can see that Luke presents a vision of happiness that is deeply rooted in the values of the Kingdom of God, where true fulfillment is found in selfless love and service to others.

Moreover, the Gospel according to Luke challenges the prevailing cultural norms of our time, which often equate happiness with personal success and pleasure. Instead, Luke's teachings encourage a shift in perspective, urging believers to seek happiness through humility, compassion, and a commitment to justice.⁴ This countercultural message is particularly relevant in today's world, where the pursuit of hedonistic happiness often leads to a sense of emptiness and dissatisfaction. By returning to the wisdom of the Gospel, individuals can find a more profound and lasting sense of happiness.

The Beatitudes: Acts of Protest and Response

The most well-known Beatitudes are the nine found in Matthew 5:1-12, but there is also an alternative set of four proclamations in Luke 6:20-23. According to redaction and source criticism studies, Luke's first three beatitudes are believed to be the closest to those spoken by the historical Jesus. The remaining beatitudes are thought to be expansions by the Evangelists, reflecting the church's experiences.⁵ These three beatitudes align closely with the theological themes of Isaiah 61:1-4, a passage Jesus had previously read in Capernaum (see Luke 4:17-20).

In terms of their literary form, the beatitudes are exclamations of praise that recognize a true state of happiness, beginning with the Hebrew term *ashré* or the Greek adjective *μακάριος* in the plural. These beatitudes are part of Jewish traditional literature and appear in both prophetic and wisdom books. Luke's version, which uses verbs and pronouns in the second person plural, is inspired by prophetic literature.⁶ The proclamation of the Gospel starts with a joyful shout celebrating the nearness of the Kingdom of God. Each beatitude consists of two parts: an announcement ("Blessed are...") and a reason ("because..."). In these reasons, Jesus provides eschatological explanations,

historical perspective.

⁴ See François Bovon. *Das Evangelium nach Lukas* (Lk 9,51-14,35). EKK III/2. Benziger & Neukirchener: Zürich & Neukirchen-Vluyn, 1996, 483.

⁵ See Ulrich Luz. *El Evangelio según san Mateo. Mt 1-7*. Biblioteca de estudios bíblicos 74-I. Salamanca: Ediciones Sígueme, 1993, 280-281; Hans D. Betz. *The Sermon on the Mount: A Commentary on the Sermon on the Mount, including the Sermon on the Plain. Matthew 5:3-7:27 and Luke 6:20-49*. ed. Adela Y. Collins. Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1995, 5-71; Gil Arbiol, 11.

⁶ Matthew, on his part, employs the third person plural, thereby aligning more closely with the wisdom style. See Luz, 281.

relating the present to the end times when the Kingdom will be fully established. Thus, the happiness described in the beatitudes has a future aspect, characteristic of the time when the Kingdom will be established. However, Jesus also speaks of a present happiness, as indicated by the participles and present verbs (ἔστιν, πεινῶντες, κλαίοντες) and the temporal adverb “now” (νῦν).

One of the most debated aspects of this text is that the blessed individuals are those whom any wise person would typically consider unfortunate (unhappy), such as the poor, the mournful, and the hungry. Through this proclamation, Jesus challenges the conventional wisdom of the world and introduces a new concept of failure and success in life. He urges his listeners to view life through the lens of the Kingdom he is announcing. The Beatitudes present a wisdom that overturns the principles of classical Greek thought. They propose an interaction between prophetic denunciation and the psalmist’s plea for the well-being of the poorest. But who would want their followers to be poor, to weep out of sadness, and to suffer hunger? Many have noted that in today’s world, some political leaders exploit people’s vulnerabilities to abuse their authority and seize their wealth.

The beatitudes are not meant to convey a political message or to endorse poverty and sadness as tools of control. On the contrary, the worldly powers are already responsible for such conditions. The opening words of the Sermon on the Plain aim to provide hope to those who suffer, assuring them that God is with them, offering love and mercy like a Father. In this sermon, Jesus refers to his audience as sons and daughters of the Most High and affirms that “your Father is merciful” (Luke 6:35-36). He later reinforces this relationship in a unique verse in Luke, where he says, “Fear not, little flock, for it has seemed good to your Father to give you the Kingdom.” This logion is not about inciting a political revolution or establishing an earthly kingdom. Instead, it calls for inner transformation, reassuring individuals that they are loved and cared for by their Creator. Additionally, the Gospel of Luke does not include the phrase “you will always have the poor” found in the other three canonical Gospels (Matthew 26:11; Mark 14:7; John 12:8). In Luke’s perspective, poverty ceases to exist when one becomes a citizen of the Kingdom and a child of the Most High. Following the proclamation of the year of grace in Luke 4:19, the human condition changes for all who believe and act accordingly. This vision is echoed in the letter of James, which states: “Has not God chosen the poor according to the world to be rich in faith and heirs of the Kingdom that he promised to those who love him?” (James 2:5).

The beatitudes’ ultimate fulfillment is an eschatological promise, yet they are realized in the present for all who humbly await their final exaltation. This simplicity and humility should be evident not only when accepting the Christian message but also in the daily lives of those who hold a joyful hope in God’s mercy in their hearts.

The Good Samaritan in Context

Unlike Matthew and Mark, who compile a series of parables into a single extended sermon, Luke distributes most of his parables throughout Jesus’ journey to Jerusalem.⁷ This method ensures that each parable is intricately connected to the specific narrative moment in which it is presented. The context of our parable involves a dialogue between Jesus and an expert in the Law (νομικός), which takes place following the successful mission of the seventy-two disciples (10:1-20) and Jesus’

⁷ The two sermons of parables are located in Mark 4:1-34 and Matthew 13:1-51. Mark includes five parables, whereas Matthew features a total of seven. In the Third Gospel, Jesus’ journey to Jerusalem spans from 9:51 to 19:23, with Jesus pausing at various points to share parables with his listeners.

praise for the revelation of the Gospel to the humble (10:21-24). This dialogue frames the parable with an introduction in verses 25-30a and a conclusion in verses 36-37.

There has been considerable discussion regarding the historical identity of the expert in the Law (νομικός) as depicted by Luke. In Matthew, the speaker is identified as a *Pharisee expert in the Law* (Mt 22:34-35), while in Mark, he is referred to as a *scribe* (Mk 12:28). Scholars debate the extent to which this lawyer was a representative of the Sanhedrin.⁸ From the text, it can be deduced that this man was a Jewish expert trained in the Law and its interpretation. The near absence of the Sadducees in Luke, except for Luke 20:27, might suggest that the term lawyer (νομικός) is used synonymously to refer to a member of this sect.⁹ However, the lawyer's recognition of Jesus as a reference point makes it difficult to associate him with such a group. In my view, the lawyer in this scene is primarily a pious Jewish man with a thorough knowledge of the Law and no other religious or political interests beyond his own salvation. This is why he sees Jesus as a master who can guide him in living his faith wisely, prompting him to inquire and test Jesus.

The lawyer approaches Jesus with a more specific question than those found in Matthew and Mark (Mt 22:36; Mk 12:28). He is not only interested in identifying the greatest commandment but also in understanding how to apply it in daily life. The lawyer recognizes that Jesus possesses both theoretical knowledge (orthodoxy) and practical wisdom (orthopraxy). Therefore, Jesus structures his response into two parts: the "what" and the "how" of the question (the τί and πῶς in v. 26). Compared to the synoptic parallels, the Lucan dialogue emphasizes the theme of happiness by addressing soteriology in relation to the daily practice of believers who seek to inherit eternal life: What do I have to do to inherit eternal Life? (v. 25).¹⁰

Jesus guides the lawyer in a manner akin to a teacher engaging in dialogue with a disciple within the Hellenistic cultural context, bearing clear similarities to Socratic maieutics. By posing questions, the Master opens new horizons for his interlocutor, allowing him to discover the correct answer on his own. This type of dialogue includes the didactic questions in verses 26 and 36, the reaffirmation in verse 28a, and the encouragement to reach a successful conclusion in verses 28b and 37.¹¹

With his final question, "Who do you think is the neighbor among the three?", Jesus shifts the perspective on identifying a neighbor. It is no longer about who receives help, but who gives it. Now, even a marginalized person like the Samaritan can be considered a neighbor if he is willing to help a stranger in need.¹² This new concept of a neighbor transcends any conventional boundaries of religious or social belonging, allowing every human being to aid others regardless of their origin or identity. Anyone moved to do good is a true neighbor. In this dialogue, the lawyer is compelled to

⁸ Cf. Daniel R. Schwartz. *Studies in the Jewish background of Christianity*. Scientific Studies on the New Testament. Tübingen: J.C.B. Mohr, 1992, 89-101; Joel B. Green. *The Gospel of Luke*. The New International Commentary on the New Testament. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1997, 427. Carlos J. Gil Arbiol, 15.

⁹ Notably, Matthew tends to pair the Pharisees with the Sadducees, whereas Luke prefers to pair the Pharisees with the Lawyers (cf. Mt 3:7; 16:1.6.11.12 with Lk 7:30; 14:3).

¹⁰ See Gil Arbiol, 15. He also interprets the term "eternal life" as another way of discussing salvation and happiness.

¹¹ Cf. Löning, Torah, 60, especially the phrase: "Er behandelt den Gegner als „Freund" im Sinne der philosophischen Gesprächskultur" and his comparison with Lk 14:10.12. See also Bovon, Evangelium III/2, 85.

¹² See Löning, Torah, 64-64; Gil Arbiol 17-18.

empathize with the half-dead victim and quickly realizes which of the three passersby acted in accordance with the commandment to love one's neighbor.

The Challenge of the Parable

The parable itself is found in verses 30-35 and depicts a travel scene on the road. Similar to Jesus and his disciples, almost all the characters in the story are in constant motion. The only exception is the innkeeper, who remains stationary in the open ending of the parable (34b-35). The traveler, the robbers, the priest, the Levite, and the Samaritan are all on the move. The main actions take place at the site of the assault, where the "half-dead" traveler now lies. Notably, the term "half-dead" (ἡμιθανής) is the final word describing the initial situation, setting the stage for the three characters who will pass by and be tested.¹³

Following the imbalance caused by the assault and violence, the story could have unfolded in one of two ways. The plot might have pursued the criminals, exploring the possibility of their capture, conviction, and the return of the stolen goods to their rightful owner. Alternatively, the focus could remain with the victim, observing whether he would be rescued or left to die. Löning perceptively notes that if the story had followed the evildoers, it would have centered on the theme of enemy love. However, by remaining with the victim, the parable emphasizes the central theme of neighborly love.¹⁴ This choice highlights the importance of compassion and assistance to those in need, regardless of their circumstances, and underscores the moral imperative to act as a true neighbor.

The parable underscores the stark contrast between witnessing evil and remaining passive and witnessing evil and taking action. It juxtaposes the behavior of two ministers of the Temple cult in Jerusalem with the prompt and determined kindness of a Samaritan, who was despised by the Jews as a schismatic. Both the priest and the Levite saw the suffering man but chose to continue on their way (vv. 31-32), highlighting their indifference to the needs of others. In contrast, both the evildoers and the Samaritan had physical contact with the victim: the former to rob and endanger his life, and the latter to provide aid and restore what was damaged. Those who approached the traveler were driven by their human emotions and desires—either the desire to deprive him of his property or the compassion to assist him. Notice the use of the verb *σπλαγχνίζομαι* in verse 33 to denote compassion. This verb appears only three times in the Gospel of Luke: here, in the resurrection of the widow's son in Nain (7:13), and in the parable of the Prodigal Son (15:20). In each instance, it describes the response of a helper upon witnessing someone in distress. The Temple servants, however, were guided by their interpretation of the correct observance of the Law, leading them to neglect the immediate needs of the suffering man.

From their perspective, the priest and the Levite believed they were acting appropriately because, at that time, Jews did not consider strangers to be their neighbors. This interpretation was based on the commandment in Leviticus 19:18, where "neighbor" referred to fellow Jews within one's community. At most, this category extended to foreigners living among them, whom the Septuagint translates as proselytes (*προσήλυτος*, see Lev 19:34). Strangers were not included in the definition of a neighbor.¹⁵ Therefore, the actions of the priest and the Levite were deemed correct, as the Torah

¹³ Löning, *Tora*, 53.

¹⁴ Löning, *Tora*, 53.

¹⁵ See John Nolland. *Luke 9:21-18:34*, Word Biblical Commentary v. 35B. Dallas: Word Books, 1993, 584; Green, 429; Gil Arbiol, 8. Löning, however, strongly opposes the notion of limiting the neighbor's identity in early Judaism. See

did not obligate them to stop and help. However, the Lucan good lawyer challenges this traditional definition of a neighbor and seeks a more inclusive interpretation. This is why his question is justified by a further inquiry into how to identify a neighbor.

Jesus challenges the narrow interpretation of the commandment of love, which is the foremost and greatest commandment in the Torah (see Mt 22:36-40). To grasp his message, one must understand the essence of love for God and neighbor, as “all the Law and the prophets depend on them” (Mt 22:40; see Rom 13:8,10).¹⁶ Through the powerful example of the Samaritan, both the lawyer and the readers are shown that the commandment of love is boundless.

Compassion and action have transformed the Samaritan’s status from scorn to respect because he acted as a true neighbor. Strict adherence to the Law and self-reliance can harden the heart, leading to disdain for those in distress. This scene illustrates that a good (a “happy”) life is only truly good when it extends to the victims, the weak, and the needy. Individual happiness is intertwined with the happiness of those we encounter, especially those experiencing hardship. Jesus emphasizes a dynamic and effective love that goes beyond mere feelings, committing to doing good and supporting those in need.

The parable can be interpreted with Christ as the Good Samaritan.¹⁷ This is one of the most common interpretations in Christian and patristic writings from the times of Marcion and Irenaeus onward, often with a strong allegorical emphasis, developing a Christological discourse rather than focusing on Jesus’ immediate message to his disciples. However, if we take this approach within the context of Luke’s Gospel, the Samaritan tends to the stranger, heals him, and entrusts him to others’ care, ensuring their well-being and promising to return with a reward. Christ proclaims the freedom of people to help anyone, regardless of their religious or political background. He demonstrates this by healing the leper, the servant of the Roman centurion, and the demon possessed (Luke 5:12-16; 7:1-10; 8:26-39). His disciples follow this example by spreading the Gospel to all nations. While evildoers leave people half-dead by the roadside, Christ comes to heal their wounds, lift them up, and provide comprehensive care.

As previously mentioned, the ending remains open. The traveler is still recuperating at the inn, under the care of those who are expected to act like the Samaritan, as he instructed them. The injured person is the only one unable to resume his journey or recover his stolen possessions. There is no mention of the fate of the criminals or their belongings. The conclusion hints at the hero’s return to restore order. The final two verses emphasize the hero’s generosity, both in the present and upon his return. The scene ends with a promise, symbolizing the hope of reward in the Second Coming: “when I return, I will repay you” (v. 35).

The Kingdom and the New Reality

The Gospel of Luke advocates for a form of happiness that is sustainable and rooted in the

Löning, Tora, 62-63.

¹⁶ Cf. Luis Heriberto Rivas. *Justicia y Amor: Fundamentos Bíblicos*. *Revista Bíblica*, vol. 67, 1-2, 2005, 21.

¹⁷ This is one of the most common interpretations in Christian and patristic writings from the times of Marcion and Irenaeus onward, often with a strong allegorical emphasis, developing a Christological discourse rather than focusing on Jesus’ immediate message to his disciples. See Joseph A. Fitzmyer. *El Evangelio según Lucas III. Traducción y comentario*. Capítulos 8,22-18,14. Madrid: Ediciones Cristiandad, 1986, 280-281.

eschatological hopes of Christians. This happiness is not tied to youth or material possessions. Instead, it transcends this world, aiming for eternal aspirations. Moreover, this happiness does not foster self-centeredness, where individuals isolate themselves to pursue personal ambitions. Rather, those who are truly happy, according to the Gospel, are those who are mindful of others' needs and actively engage in serving others out of love.

In today's world, the term "aporophobia" has been coined to describe the rejection of the poor.¹⁸ Additionally, mercy has long been a virtue criticized by secular philosophical thought.¹⁹ Moreover, "prosperity theologies" are gaining more followers, as they justify accumulating wealth under the pretext of better aiding those in need. Within this context, the Gospel of Luke is distinguished as the Gospel of mercy, emphasizing the transformative power of imitating God's merciful actions towards those in need.

In both texts, humanity is overwhelmed by the violence of this world, whether through hunger or attacks by malicious individuals. This situation demands a radical change. Jesus warns that merely observing others' suffering without taking action is futile. Even expressing gratitude to God for one's own blessings and better circumstances is insufficient for salvation, either for oneself or others. Religious righteousness that ignores the plight of strangers leads nowhere. Therefore, we need someone to bless those who suffer and offer them a way out of their injustice and deprivation. This approach can bring happiness to both the helper and the recipient. The Gospel of Luke clearly states that hoarding and accumulating goods for personal gain is futile: "But God said to him: 'You fool, this very night you are going to die. And for whom will what you have heaped up be?'" (Luke 12:20). In the selfish model promoted by contemporary culture, the world can only descend into unbearable chaos, where mutual trust becomes impossible. Hence, it is more crucial than ever to emphasize the countercultural message of the Gospel.

In the Gospel of Matthew, Jesus urges the faithful to "be perfect as your Father who is in heaven is perfect" (Mt 5:48). Scholars agree that this command does not call for a change in one's nature, but rather in one's actions.²⁰ Thus, being perfect means acting perfectly, emulating the Heavenly Father by doing good and offering salvation to both the righteous and the unrighteous. The Gospel of Luke, however, uses the term merciful, emphasizing God's mercy in rescuing humanity, forgiving sins, and offering new life: "Be merciful, as your Father is merciful" (Lk 6:36). Ultimately, both versions of this teaching strongly encourage listeners to practice fraternal love, humble and generous service, and to show mercy towards the poor, as the lawyer deduced in the final verse of the

¹⁸ Cf. Adela Cortina. *Aporofobia, el rechazo al pobre: un desafío para la democracia*. Paidós: Barcelona, 2017. "The concept of aporophobia was coined by the philosopher Dr Cortina in 1995 and entered the Spanish RAE dictionary in 2017, defined as a 'phobia of poor and disadvantaged people.' According to Dr Cortina herself, aporophobia refers to a 'rejection, aversion, fear, and contempt towards the poor and the helpless who, at least in appearance, cannot bring anything good in return,' with a clear component of discrimination and prejudice." From: Juan Albacete Maza. *Aporophobia and Its Social Impact*. In: IQS Universitat Ramon Llull. <https://iqs.edu>. Seen on April 28, 2024.

¹⁹ Criticism of a judge showing mercy can be traced back to Socrates. Similarly, Nietzsche also critiques mercy and compassion in his writings. See Plato, *Apology of Socrates 34c and 35b*; Friedrich Nietzsche *Así habló Zaratustra: un libro para todos y para nadie*. El libro de bolsillo. Madrid: Alianza, 2003, 139 and especially 142: "God is dead; because of his compassion for men, God has died" (translation by the author). See also Löning, Tora, 68-69, particularly footnote 24.

²⁰ See Rivas, 20 and William D. Davies and Dale C. Allison Jr. *The Gospel according to Saint Matthew*. Vol. 1. T&T Clark: Edinburgh, 1988, 563.

dialog (Luke 10:37).

Conclusions

At the outset of his proclamation with the Beatitudes and the beginning of his journey to Jerusalem, Jesus emphasizes the necessity of completely renouncing the wisdom of this world to embrace the saving wisdom of the Kingdom. For Jesus and his followers, the Kingdom becomes an increasingly tangible reality, starting with its announcement in Capernaum and the opening of the Sermon on the Plain. Consequently, worldly values are inverted and redefined. The weakest and most marginalized now become the primary recipients of future blessings. Both texts serve as an eschatological promise, already fulfilled through Jesus' death and resurrection. His followers are now called to live in service to others, bearing true witness to the Kingdom.

Bibliography

- Albacete Maza, Juan. *Aporophobia and Its Social Impact*. IQS Universitat Ramon Llull. <https://iqs.edu>. Seen on April 28, 2024.
- Betz, Hans D. *The Sermon on the Mount: A Commentary on the Sermon on the Mount, including the Sermon on the Plain. Matthew 5:3-7:27 and Luke 6:20-49*. ed. Adela Y. Collins. Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1995.
- Bovon, François. *Das Evangelium nach Lukas (Lk 9,51-14,35)*. EKK III/2. Benziger & Neukirchener: Zürich & Neukirchen-Vluyn, 1996.
- Cortina, Adela. *Aporofobia, el rechazo el pobre: un desafío para la democracia*. Paidós: Barcelona, 2017.
- Davies, William D. and Dale C. Allison Jr. *The Gospel according to Saint Matthew*. Vol. 1. T&T Clark: Edinburgh, 1988.
- Fitzmyer, Joseph A. *El Evangelio según Lucas III. Traducción y comentario. Capítulos 8,22-18,14*. Madrid: Ediciones Cristiandad, 1986, 280-281.
- Gil Arbiol, Carlos J. El Buen Samaritano y la proximidad del herido: La aportación del naciente cristianismo a la búsqueda de la felicidad. *Carthaginensia* 40, 77, 2024, 1-23. <https://doi-org.ezsecureaccess.balamand.edu.lb/10.62217/carth.581>.
- Green, Joel B. *The Gospel of Luke*. The New International Commentary on the New Testament. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1997.
- Helliwell, J. F., Layard, R., Sachs, J. D., De Neve, J.-E., Aknin, L. B., & Wang, S. (Eds.). *World Happiness Report 2024*. University of Oxford: Wellbeing Research Centre, 2024. <https://worldhappiness.report/ed/2024/>.
- Löning, Karl. Die Tora als Weg zum ewigen Leben nach Lk 10,25-37. In: Arnold Angenendt & Herbert Vorgrimler (Ed.). *Sie wandern von Kraft zu Kraft. Aufbrüche, Wege, Begegnungen. Festgabe für Bischof Reinhard Lettmann*. Butzon & Bercker: Kevelaer, 1993, 49-71.
- Luz, Ulrich. *El Evangelio según san Mateo. Mt 1-7*. Biblioteca de estudios bíblicos 74-I. Salamanca: Ediciones Sígueme, 1993.

- Mate, Reyes. *La razón de los vencidos*. Barcelona: Anthropos, 1991.
- Nietzsche, Friedrich. *Así habló Zaratustra: un libro para todos y para nadie*. El libro de bolsillo. Madrid: Alianza, 2003.
- Nolland, John. *Luke 9:21-18:34*, Word Biblical Commentary v. 35B. Dallas: Word Books, 1993.
- Rivas, Luis Heriberto. Justicia y Amor: Fundamentos Bíblicos. *Revista Bíblica* 67, 1-2, 2005, pp. 5-29.
- Schwartz, Daniel R. *Studies in the Jewish background of Christianity*. Scientific Studies on the New Testament. Tübingen: J.C.B. Mohr, 1992.
- Spadaro, Antonio & Marcelo Figueroa. Teología de la Prosperidad. El peligro de un “Evangelio diferente.” *La Civiltà Cattolica*. 29 de abril de 2022. <https://www.laciviltacattolica.es/>.
- Vázquez, Xosé Gabriel. Opinión. Informe Mundial de la Felicidad. En: *Economía Digital Galicia*. <https://www.economiadigital.es/galicia/opinion/informe-mundial-de-la-felicidad.html>.